

Disease resistance

A promising donor for blast resistance

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Leaf blast is one of the most important rice diseases in Kerala, and Pattambi is a hot spot for the disease. While screening prerelease cultures for disease resistance, we found that KAU1907, a short-

duration, white-kerneled, medium-tall culture from the cross Bhavani/Triveni scored 1 in a trial where the national check variety Vani scored 6, using the 0-9 scale. Tests in three subsequent trials confirmed this highly resistant reaction of the culture (see table). This finding is significant because KAU1907 has wide adaptability to important seasons and cropping situations in Kerala, including rainfed uplands. □

Reaction of KAU1907 to leaf blast at Pattambi, India.

Variety	Disease score (0-9 scale)			
	1981-82		1982-83	
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
Triveni	5	5	9	7
Kannagi	9	3	7	3
Vani	6	1	1	1
KAU1907	1	0	0	0

Antibiotic activity of rice agglutinin

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Agglutination or immobilization of plant pathogenic bacteria in several hosts, including rice, has been reported. We isolated a small molecular weight protein from rice seeds and leaves that showed agglutination and antibiotic activity. The rice agglutination factor (RAF) was isolated from cultivars TN1 and BJ1. Agglutination was determined by the agglutination drop test. Antibiotic activity was

Antibiotic activity and agglutination titers of the rice agglutinin factor (RAF) derived from the seeds and leaves of some rice cultivars.^a

Source	Av diam of inhibition zones (mm) against		Agglutination titers against	
			<i>X. c. pv. oryzae</i> (H470)	<i>E. amylovora</i> (E8)
	<i>X. c. pv. oryzae</i>	<i>E. amylovora</i> (E8)		
TN1 seed	8	10	1:64	1:64
TN1 leaf	10	0	n.t.	n.t.
BJ1 seed	10	8	1:256	1:128
RJ1 leaf	16	7	n.t.	n.t.

^an.t. = not tested.

measured, using the cylinder-plate method, against a virulent strain of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (H470) and an avirulent acapsular strain of *Erwinia amylovora* (E8) (see table).

The RAF derived from BJ1 had higher antibiotic activity than that from TN1.

The RAF from BJ1 seeds also was higher than that from TN1. It is likely that the RAF plays a role in the disease resistance capability of certain cultivars not only by its agglutinating activity but also by antibiotic activity. □

Varietal resistance to leaf blast and sheath blight at Pattambi, India

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Leaf blast (Bl) and sheath blight (ShB) are two major rice diseases in Kerala. During 1981-82 kharif, 388 cultivars of National Screening Nursery I were tested for Bl and ShB resistance at RARS, Pattambi, which is a hot spot location for both diseases. Screening for Bl used UBN pattern and was under upland situations with Pusa 2-21 as the susceptible check. ShB screening was under transplanted conditions with Jyothy as susceptible

Rice cultures with multiple resistance to leaf blast and sheath blight at RARS, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Entry	Cross	Reaction to	
		Leaf blast	Sheath blight
TNAU17005	Dasal/IR20	R	MR
RNR74822	Sona/Monoharsali	R	R
R245-30-41	OBS677/IR2078-436-3-5	R	R
HPU2205	ASH/IR1820-17-1	R	R
HPU2206	-do-	R	R
HPU2203	AS11/IR1820-210-2-//CH1039	R	R
IET6080	-do-	R	MR
RP1015-12-10-3-1-1	Sona/Monoharsali	MR	MR
R161-3179	Kali monch 64/Sona	MR	MR
KMP8	-do-	MR	MR
KMP41	-do-	MR	MR
RNR82249	Tella	hamsa/Rasi MR	MR
RP1015-45-117-1	Sona/Monoharsali	MR	MR
RP1015-38-85-1	-do-	MR	MR